

Acquisition and Utilization of Digital Skills by Librarians for Effective Service Delivery in University Libraries in North-Central Nigeria

by

Dr. Joseph Ahemba Gbuushi

University Library and Information Services, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshi Adasu University, Makurdi

Prof. Margaret N. Ngwuchukwu

Department of Library and Information Science, Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

Dr. Mbalamen Susan Ianna

University Library and Information Services, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshi Adasu University, Makurdi

Dr. Christiana Mnena Jootar

Department of Library and Information Science, Faculty of Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

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Abstract

The study investigated the acquisition and utilization of digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-central Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine the mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria and also to find out digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. A descriptive survey method was employed, with a population of 243 librarians from 15 public university libraries. No sample was done as a result of the manageable size of the population. The instruments for data collection were questionnaire and interview. The findings showed that, the acquisition and utilization of digital skills to high extent contributes to effective service delivery, regardless of librarians' years of experience, the also showed that using library management software and systems is the digital skill highly used and it has no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. based on highest educational qualification. Based on the findings, it was concluded that university libraries in North-Central Nigeria should invest in targeted training programmes focused on enhancing librarians' proficiency in essential digital skills, including library management software, emerging technologies, online resource evaluation, digital communication, and social media, to improve service delivery; university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria.

Keyword: Digital Skills Acquisition, Librarian Competencies, University Library Services Digital Service Delivery, and North-Central Nigeria.

Introduction

University libraries act as knowledge centres, giving researchers, instructors, and students access to academic services, research assistance, and information resources. The traditional function of libraries has changed to provide digital services with the introduction of information and communication technologies (ICTs) (Bhoi, 2017). Librarians must have the necessary digital skills to manage electronic resources, provide online services, and advance digital literacy in order to fulfil the demands of the digital age (Khumalo, Rajkoomar, & Rajagopaul, 2022). This study explores the ways in which librarians learn digital skills and the domains in which they are used to provide efficient services in university libraries. Digital skills are acquired by librarians using both official and informal learning approaches. This is a fundamental approach these days, technology-based courses covering subjects like database administration, metadata, and digital library design are incorporated into the curricula of library schools and information science programs. Universities also give employees access to official training courses, workshops, and seminars so they may keep up to date on digital trends and master new technology. Professional development and organised learning depend on these programs (Ahmed, Gama, & Farouk, (2024).

However, a significant problem exists regarding digital skills among librarians: many lack adequate competencies in areas such as ICT infrastructure management, digital content creation, data security, and advanced information retrieval, leading to inefficiencies in delivering modern library services like electronic resource management and online user support (Baro, Obaro, & Aduba, 2019). This skills gap may hinder the ability of libraries to fully transition to digital environments and support academic communities effectively (Martzoukou, 2021).

This problem persists in North-Central Nigeria primarily due to challenges such as inconsistent power supply, poor ICT facilities, limited access to training opportunities, funding constraints, and inadequate infrastructure, which collectively impede the acquisition and application of digital skills among librarians (Ogunode, Okwelogu, & Olatunde-Aiyedun, 2021). Regional disparities in technology adoption and professional development resources exacerbate these issues, making it difficult for librarians to keep pace with global digital trends (Khumalo, Rajkoomar, & Rajagopaul, 2022).

The current study fills a critical gap by specifically examining the modes of digital skills acquisition and their utilization for effective service delivery in university libraries within North-Central Nigeria, a region underrepresented in existing literature that often focuses on southern states or general national overviews without localized insights into practical application and barriers (Ahmed, Gama, & Farouk, 2024 Khumalo, Rajkoomar, & Rajagopaul, 2022). This study is justified as it addresses the pressing need to enhance the acquisition and utilization of digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central Nigeria, ultimately contributing to improved academic support, resource accessibility, and digital transformation in higher education institutions within the region

Objectives

1. Determine the mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria
2. Find out digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria

Research Questions

Hypotheses

- Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians in the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification.
- Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians in the areas reference services' digital skills is applied for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on age category.

Literature Review

University Libraries

University libraries are established to provide relevant information service to members of the university community. Services provided by the university libraries reflect the articulated aim and objectives of its parent institutions, which include teaching, learning and research activities. Eje and Dushu (2018) stated that, traditionally, university libraries and other information centres have been concerned with the objective of acquiring, organising, storing, preserving and disseminating information resources that will be transmitted to future generations for easy access. To achieve this role, librarians have to organise and preserve both the physical and the intellectual content of the information media. This however, will be a futile effort if either the documents themselves or the information which they contain are not readily accessible for future use.

The holdings of university libraries are therefore invaluable heritage of mankind as they preserve facts, ideals, thoughts, cultural heritage resources, research outputs and evidences of human development in various formats. Ike et al (2023) noted that university libraries are part of an educational process and have a mission which is derived from the institution they are established to serve. In order for university libraries to provide efficient, contemporary services, digital literacy is essential. These are the skills necessary to locate, assess, produce, and share information using digital technology. The way libraries function and serve their communities is changing as a result of the development and use of these talents.

Methods for Learning Digital Skills

Both formal and informal learning strategies are used to help university workers and librarians develop their digital skills. According Arya and Gupta (2018) formal education approach is fundamental, technology-based courses covering subjects like digital library design, database administration, and metadata are now incorporated into the curricula of library schools and information science programs. For employees to stay up to date with digital trends and understand new technology, universities also offer structured training programs, workshops, and seminars. For professional development and organised learning, these programs are crucial. Ayoku and Okafor (2015) opined that additional typical methods by which librarians learn useful abilities are trial and error; librarians gain knowledge by trying out new devices, platforms, and software, colleague support; one important strategy is to learn from more seasoned colleagues, which promotes a cooperative setting for talent exchange, Self-Paced Learning.

To acquire certain skills, librarians employ user manuals, tutorials, and online learning environments (such as Coursera or LinkedIn Learning) and exposure to technology; employees learn skills naturally when they have access to and use digital technologies in their regular work.

This involves engaging with new mobile technology, employing institutional structures, and using social media. Bajpai and Margam (2019) agreed that acquisition of Digital Skills forms the foundation of the diagram, detailing the various pathways through which librarians develop the competencies needed for modern library services. This begins with self-study, where librarians take the initiative to learn independently, reflecting a personal commitment to skill enhancement. On-the-job training offers hands-on learning opportunities within the workplace, allowing librarians to acquire skills through mentorship, practice, and real-world experiences. Workshops and seminars provide structured platforms for gaining targeted skills, often facilitated by experts in the field. Similarly, conferences enable librarians to exchange ideas, share best practices, and keep up with emerging trends. The advent of technology has made online courses a significant method for learning, providing flexibility and access to a vast array of specialized knowledge. Also, the category of other methods of digital skills acquisition indicates alternative methods of skill acquisition, emphasizing the diversity of approaches available to librarians.

Areas of Application of Digital Skills for Effective Service Delivery

Almost every facet of contemporary university library services uses digital skills to improve user experience and efficiency. Management of Information and Resources; digitisation and digital repositories is one of the area Librarians create online archives and institutional repositories by scanning and digitising physical collections using their digital expertise. This enables a worldwide audience to access rare books, theses, and other unique items (.Chukwueke & Idris, 2023). Mobile Services and the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) are other areas that librarians utilise their digital skills to update and manage the OPAC, which makes the library's collection searchable and available online.

Additionally, they create and oversee mobile apps and services that let consumers check their accounts, renew books, and get alerts on their devices. Bajpai and Margam (2019) highlighted areas as through the use of digital skills, users can receive help with their research from any location by using Ask a Librarian services, email, and instant messaging, communication outreach, technical administrative tasks, user training digital literacy education, Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) and Mobile Services. In order to be relevant in the digital age, university libraries must effectively acquire and apply digital skills. By adopting these skills, librarians can offer creative, superior services that satisfy the changing demands of their patrons, eventually enhancing the university community's academic performance and research production.

Effective Service Delivery

Service delivery in a university library refers to the process of providing high-quality assistance to meet the needs and expectations of library users. It encompasses offering professional expertise, delivering valuable information resources, and supporting individuals in their academic and research endeavours. Effective service delivery is achieved when a library successfully meets or exceeds the needs, expectations, and desired outcomes of its users (Bashir, Hameed, Bari & Ullah, 2021; Anania, 2023). This involves librarians developing, deploying, and managing information resources and services using digital technologies, thereby ensuring that users receive increased value from the library's offerings (Oyedokun, Oyewumi, Akanbi & Laaro, 2018). On the acquisition of digital skills, Onakoya et al (2023) put that majority of the respondents maintained that they acquire these skills via seminars, training and retraining by their colleagues, self-sponsorship, and trial and error. Accordingly, most of acquired digital skills are through in-service training to acquire more education officially, sponsorship by the library to

workshops/seminars, in house training (inviting experts to teach digital skills, official sponsorship to acquire computer/digital skills, self-sponsor to workshops/seminars on digital, self-sponsor to learn computer/digital skills. According to Gupta (2024), new skills are acquired through various ways, such as observation, experience, and instruction.

Furthermore, Pradhan and Rai (2023) highlight several initiatives for acquiring digital skills, essential for the modern library and information science (LIS) professionals. One key approach is through training and professional development programmes. Libraries and professional organisations can offer workshops, training sessions, and online courses tailored to enhance digital capabilities. These programmes should address various dimensions of digital skills and specific challenges librarians face, empowering them to navigate the digital age effectively. Another significant initiative is fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing among LIS professionals. Creating communities of practice, online forums, and social networks can facilitate the exchange of best practices and experiences related to digital capabilities. Such collaborative efforts can help librarians stay updated with the latest technological advancements and improve their digital literacy collectively.

Additionally, embedding digital capability development into library science curricula is crucial. Educational institutions can ensure that future LIS professionals acquire essential digital skills by integrating these competencies into their programmes. Moreover, the availability of video tutorials, manuals, software, and online lectures provides ample resources for professionals to continually learn and update their digital skills, fostering a culture of continuous improvement in the field. By focusing on these varied strategies for digital skill acquisition, librarians can ensure they are well-prepared to meet the demands of the digital age. Furthermore, understanding the broader classification of learning methods, as outlined by Fergusson (2022), can provide additional insights into how these digital skills can be effectively cultivated.

Methods

The design of study is descriptive survey research design. The area of this study is North-Central, Nigeria. The population of this study is 243 librarians drawn from the 15 university libraries under the study. The entire population of 243 librarians in public libraries in North-Central Nigeria is used for the study hence, the study employed census survey method. Two instruments use for data collection are: questionnaire and interview. Quantitative and qualitative techniques were used for the data analyse. This gives room for triangulation of the data obtained from the field. Quantitative data is analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 to answer research questions.

Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Hypothesis 1-3 were tested using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Where P value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected as it implies a significance difference. On the other hand, where the p value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted as it shows no differences exist. For the qualitative data, the interview responses were transcribed and coded. The responses were analysed using thematic analysis to identify patterns in the meaning of the data to find themes base on the objectives of the research as presented in the results.

Results

Research Question One

What is the mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean response of mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, N=234.

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	SD	R	Dec.
1	Self-study	161	60	9	4	3.62	0.65	1 st	SA
2	On-the-job learning experiences	107	105	18	4	3.35	0.70	3 rd	A
3	Formal training programmes	132	80	10	12	3.42	0.80	2 nd	A
4	Workshops and seminars	110	100	11	13	3.31	0.80	4 th	A
5	Mentors or experts	100	96	30	8	3.23	0.80	5 th	A
6	Peer learning	100	95	31	8	3.23	0.81	5 th	A
7	Online courses	112	83	17	22	3.22	0.94	7 th	A
8	Collaboration	102	91	23	18	3.18	0.90	8 th	A
9	The university library adequate resources provision	98	90	32	14	3.16	0.88	9 th	A
Cluster Mean						3.30	0.48		A

Key: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard Deviation, SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, R = Rank, Dec. = Decision.

Table 1 displays the mean responses of mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. From the table, item 1 has mean value of 3.62, which falls within the range strongly agree mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery. In contrast, items 2-9 have mean values of 3.42-3.16, which falls within the range agree mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery. From the table, among the mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery self-study ($\bar{x} = 3.62$, SD = 0.65) ranked first, formal training programmes ($\bar{x} = 3.42$, SD = 0.80) ranked second, on-the-job learning experiences ($\bar{x} = 3.35$, SD = 0.70) came third, workshops and seminars ($\bar{x} = 3.31$, SD = 0.80) ranked fourth, among others while the least is the university library adequate resources provision ($\bar{x} = 3.16$, SD = 0.88). Other modes of acquiring digital skills are mentors or experts ($\bar{x} = 3.23$, SD = 0.80), peer learning ($\bar{x} = 3.23$, SD = 0.81), online courses ($\bar{x} = 3.22$, SD = 0.94), and collaboration ($\bar{x} = 3.18$, SD = 0.90).

The findings from the quantitative data in Table 4 above indicate that, self-study is the major mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery. Other modes of acquiring digital skills are on-the-job learning experiences, and formal training programmes among others. The finding corresponds with comments by respondents interviewed. With regard to items 1, 2 and 3 in Table 4 above, RESPONDENT 2 have this to say: "It is mostly personal. It's your personal attempt because as you know, most of our institutions are no longer sponsoring us, even for our local and normal conferences and workshops. So, we attempt this on our own, through other institutions... I acquired them personally, paid for them, and have them". In correspond, RESPONDENT 9 emphasizes that: "some of those skills are self-taught. So, some are through

formal training. Some are from workshops. Some are from webinars and online courses. And as I said, some are on the job learning". Also, RESPONDENT 3 notes that: "through formal education", "through professional development like workshops and seminars," and "on-the-job training" where staff learn digital skills. RESPONDENT 6, also mention that "professional development such as attending workshops, webinars, and conferences". On a general note, RESPONDENT 1, 5 and 9 notes that librarians mostly acquired digital skills through self-development efforts and formal training. This implies that respondents agreed that self-study, on-the-job learning experiences, and formal training programmes among all the items in Table 4 above are the modes of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians in the mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of librarians in the mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery based on highest educational qualification

Highest Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
BLS/B.Sc	116	3.31	0.40
MLS	100	3.31	0.52
Ph.D	18	3.21	0.72
Total	234	3.30	0.48

Table 6: ANOVA of the Difference in the mean response of librarians in the mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery in university libraries based on highest educational qualification

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	0.166	2	0.083	0.354	0.702	NS
Within Groups	54.227	231	0.235			
Total	54.393	233				

Table 2 shows ANOVA result of the difference in the mean response of librarians in the mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification. The result showed an f-ratio of 0.35 with the significant value of 0.70. Since the significant value is greater than 0.05 set as level of significance, it means that the null hypothesis is accepted. Inference drawn is that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians in the mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification. This implies that librarians' highest educational qualification is not a significant factor in determining the mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria.

Research Question Two

What are the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean response of digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries, N=234.

S/N	Item Statement	HU	MU	LU	NU	\bar{x}	SD	R	Dec.
1	Use library management software and systems	149	73	9	3	3.56	0.71	1 st	HU
2	Navigating and utilizing online catalogues	114	95	17	8	3.31	0.75	5 th	MU
3	Navigating and utilizing digital archives	115	85	31	3	3.31	0.81	5 th	MU
4	Use of electronic resources to support academic researchers	105	81	37	11	3.33	0.74	4 th	MU
5	Use of online databases	120	84	21	9	3.35	0.77	3 rd	MU
6	Use of e-books and e-journals	163	58	9	4	3.40	0.74	2 nd	HU
7	Online training	107	96	26	5	3.30	0.82	7 th	MU
8	Social media and online platforms	112	91	25	6	3.24	0.91	8 th	MU
9	Securing online library resources	102	96	30	6	3.16	0.83	9 th	MU
Cluster Mean						3.33	0.46		MU

Key: N = \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard Deviation, HU = Highly Used, MU = Moderately Used, R = Rank, Dec. = Decision.

Table 3 displays the mean responses of digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. From the table, items 1 and 6 have mean values of 3.56 and 3.40, which fall within the range of digital skills highly used by librarians for effective service delivery. In contrast, items 2-9 have mean values range from 3.31-3.16, which fall within the range of digital skills moderately used by librarians for effective service delivery. This implies that all the 9 digital skills presented in Table 7 above are digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery. The standard deviation of items 1-9 ranges from 0.71-0.91. This shows that the respondents were close to one another in their opinion regarding the digital skills they use for effective service delivery. From the result, use library management software and systems ($\bar{x} = 3.56$, SD = 0.71) is ranked first, use of e-books and e-journals ($\bar{x} = 3.40$, SD = 0.74) is ranked second among others, while. securing online library resources ($\bar{x} = 3.16$, SD = 0.83) is ranked last.

The findings from the quantitative data in Table 7 above indicates that, using library management software and systems is digital skill highly used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. Other skills such as navigating and utilizing online catalogs, and navigating and utilizing digital archives among others are moderately used. The finding corresponds with comments by respondents interviewed. With regard to items 1 in Table 7 above, RESPONDENT 5 have this to say: “*library practice uses specific software*” for item 4, 5 and 6 RESPONDENT 6 explains that “*Librarians use advanced search techniques and academic databases*” and manage resources like e-books “*JSTOR for accessing academic journals, then books and primary sources*” and “*open source LMS for various library functions*”

This implies skills in navigate library management software and systems, competence in the use of e-books and e-journals, ability to use of online databases, skills in navigating and utilizing online catalogues, and navigating and skills in utilizing digital archives among all the items in Table 7 above are the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians in the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of respondents in the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery based on highest educational qualification

Highest Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
BLS/B.Sc	116	3.32	0.43
MLS	100	3.36	0.46
Ph.D	18	3.26	0.61
Total	234	3.33	0.46

Table 4: ANOVA of the Difference in the mean response of librarians in the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries based on highest educational qualification

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	0.193	2	0.096	0.461	0.631	NS
Within Groups	48.285	231	0.209			
Total	48.477	233				

Table 4 shows ANOVA result of the difference in the mean response of librarians in the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification. The result showed an f-ratio of 0.46 with the significant value of 0.63. Since the significant value is greater than 0.05 set as level of significance, it means that the null hypothesis is accepted. Inference drawn is that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians in the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification. This implies that librarians' highest educational qualification is not a significant factor in determining the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria.

Discussion and Conclusion

Mode of Acquiring Digital Skills by Librarians for Effective Service Delivery in University Libraries in North-Central, Nigeria

Research question three sought to find out the modes of acquiring digital skills by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. The result shows that, the major mode of acquiring digital skills by librarians is self-study. Other modes of acquiring digital skills are on-the-job learning experiences, and formal training programmes among others. However, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians in the mode of acquiring digital skills for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on the highest educational qualification. The likely reason for librarians relies heavily on self-study to acquire digital skills may be due to the availability of online resources and tutorials that allow them to learn at their own pace and convenience or it could be limited or inaccessible of sponsorship. On-the-job learning experiences is likely to be effective because it allows librarians to apply new skills immediately, reinforcing their learning through practice. The finding may be feasible because digital skills acquisition often depends on practical experience, self-motivation, access to learning resources, and workplace support, among other factors, rather than depending solely on formal educational qualifications. Librarians, regardless of their highest educational qualification, may equally benefit from self-study, on-the-job learning, and formal training programmes. This indicates that the different modes of acquiring digital skills are available and may be effective for librarians regardless of their level of educational qualification.

These findings are consistent with Shidi and Nwachukwu's (2015) findings, which indicated that librarians acquired all the basic skills required to work in a digital library through self-efforts and sponsorship by the library. In support, Oyovwe-Tinuoye et al. (2021) show that self-sponsorship was the primary method used by the majority of respondents to acquire ICT skills. Onakoya et al. (2023) emphasize that the majority of respondents maintained that they acquired these skills via seminars, training and retraining by their colleagues, self-sponsorship, and trial and error. Also, Imam, Muhammad, Abba, and Ijiekhuamhen (2020) show that on-the-job training, in-house training, participation in professional associations, lectures/discussions, and exercises, and job rotation are the major methods of building capacity among library and information professionals. As Gupta (2024) summarizes, new skills are acquired through various ways, such as observation, experience, and instruction.

The finding of the study therefore shows that the acquisition of digital skills among librarians in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, is complex and not significantly influenced by their highest educational qualifications. Instead, it shows that librarians can effectively acquire these skills through various modes such as self-study, on-the-job learning, and formal training programmes. This suggests that practical experience, self-motivation, and access to learning resources are crucial factors in developing digital competencies, regardless of formal education. The findings suggest that training programmes for librarians should be diverse and flexible, accommodating different learning styles and educational backgrounds. Libraries should provide opportunities for continuous learning, regardless of a librarian's formal education level.

Digital Skills Used by Librarians for Effective Service Delivery in University Libraries in North-Central, Nigeria

Research question four sought to identify the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. The results show that, using library management software and systems is the digital skill highly used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria. Other skills such as navigating and utilizing online catalogs, and navigating and utilizing digital archives among others are moderately used. However, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of librarians with respect to the digital skills used by librarians for effective service delivery in university libraries in North-Central, Nigeria, based on highest educational qualification.

The finding is feasible because the digital skills required for effective service delivery in university libraries are typically standardized and essential across all educational levels. These skills, such as navigating library management software, using e-books and e-journals, and accessing online databases, are fundamental to modern library operations. As a result, regardless of the librarians' highest educational qualifications, they are expected to possess and utilize these skills effectively. Therefore, it is logical that there would be no significant difference in the mean responses regarding the use of digital skills based on educational qualifications.

The findings align with David-West's (2022) study, which revealed that there is no significant difference between digital literacy and the utilization of online platforms for teaching by LIS educators in universities in Rivers State. Additionally, Daniels, Humphrey, and Nsirim (2023) found a significant relationship between web application skills, library networking skills, cloud technology skills, and effective library service delivery. The findings also agree with the study by Nwokedi, Nwokedi, Amkpa, and Ogugua (2017b), which showed that librarians' competence in file management and its use has a significant effect on their service delivery. This might suggest that librarians and libraries in North-Central are investing in regular training sessions and workshops to keep their staff updated with the latest digital tools and technologies. This also shows that skills are likely part of the core training and continuous professional development programmes for librarians, ensuring that all staff members, regardless of their educational background, are equipped to handle the demands of modern library services.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the ongoing development and use of digital skills by library employees is inextricably related to the efficient provision of services inside university libraries. A strong skill set is the result of this multifaceted process, which includes self-directed learning, continuing professional development, and formal education programs. From maintaining digital collections and improving information retrieval to offering enhanced reference services and encouraging digital literacy among professors and students, these skills are then strategically deployed across a number of crucial sectors. As technology continues to change the academic scene, it is not only advantageous but also essential to actively cultivate these skills. Through the adoption of a lifelong learning culture, university libraries may guarantee their continued centrality to the academic purpose while offering creative, pertinent, and efficient services that satisfy the ever-changing demands of their communities.

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